

21GRD08 SoMMet

D8: Good practice guide for interdisciplinary data fusion of soil moisture measurements on multiple scales

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**METROLOGY
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Deliverable **D8** of project 21GRD08 SoMMet

Good practice guide for interdisciplinary data fusion of soil moisture measurements on multiple scales

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Glossary

A146: Sentinel-1 ascending orbit 146

a.s.l.: above sea level

ASCAT: Advanced SCATterometer

CCI: Climate Change Initiative

CEOS: Committee on Earth Observation Satellites

CRNS: Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensor / Sensing

CRNSs: Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensors

D7: Deliverable 7

D8: Deliverable 8

D168: Sentinel-1 descending orbit 168

ELBARA: European Space Agency L-band Radiometer

ESA: European Space Agency

ESSD: Earth System Science Data

EUMETSAT: European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites

GEO: Group on Earth Observations

GRD: Ground Range Detected

HPIC: High-Pressure Ionisation Chamber

HR: High Resolution

IDW: Inverse Distance Weighting

IW: Interferometric Wide

LWF: Linear Weight Fusion

MetOp: Meteorological Operational platform

NASA: National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NISAR: NASA–ISRO Synthetic Aperture Radar

NN: Neural Network

PR2: profile probe

PS: Point-scale

QA4EO: Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation

R: Pearson correlation coefficient

RMSE: Root Mean Square Error

ROSE-L: Radar Observing System for Europe in L-band

RS: Remote sensing

RSS-131: Reuter-Stokes ionisation chamber model 131

SAR: Synthetic Aperture Radar

S-1: Sentinel-1

SM: Soil moisture

SMAP: Soil Moisture Active Passive

SMOS: Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity

SMOSAR: Soil Moisture retrieval algorithm for Sentinel-1

SRU: Spatial Representativeness Uncertainty

STCD: Short-Term Change Detection

TbH: brightness temperature, horizontal polarization

TbV: brightness temperature, vertical polarization

UBRMSE: Unbiased Root Mean Square Error

VH: Vertical transmit – Horizontal receive polarization

VV: Vertical transmit – Vertical receive polarization

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Summary

This document, deliverable D8, is the last of eight technical deliverables of the project 21GRD08 SoMMet (hereafter: SoMMet). The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States (Funder name: European Partnership on Metrology; Funder ID: 10.13039/100019599; Grant number: 21GRD08 SoMMet).

The document summarises the activities of the SoMMet project's Task 4.2., *Implementation of data fusion of soil moisture measurements on multiple scales*.

The availability of soil moisture measurements across multiple spatial and temporal scales, e.g., from satellite and ground instruments, poses the challenge of effectively integrating them. One approach involves using one dataset as a reference to assess the uncertainty of another dataset (validation). Another method is to combine multi-scale soil moisture datasets to leverage each dataset's strengths in terms of resolution, accuracy, or coverage, to produce more accurate, spatially distributed estimation of soil moisture (data fusion).

Both validation and data fusion are tackled in this report, and a proof-of-concept integrating satellite and ground soil moisture is shown. Highlights are drawn in the Conclusions section.

In the Appendix, a test case investigating a data fusion method based on a Neural Network technique is also provided. The test case investigates the possibility of using measured gamma radiation dose values in the natural environment to retrieve soil moisture.

1 Introduction

The advent of satellite-based remote sensing, particularly during the last decades, has led to a huge amount of research in assessing the extent to which such systems can provide accurate maps of soil moisture (SM) from space.

Measurements of SM at global scales and at spatial resolutions of $25 \times 25 \text{ km}^2$ or coarser and high temporal resolution (2-3 days), using radiometers or scatterometer, are currently provided, for example, as products of the Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS) mission of the European Space Agency (ESA) (Kerr et al., 2010), the Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) mission of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) (Entekhabi et al., 2010), and the Advanced SCATterometer (ASCAT) system aboard the Meteorological Operational (MetOp) platform of the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) (Wagner et al., 2013). In the last decade, the Copernicus European Radar Observatory Sentinel-1 (S-1) mission, characterized by an unprecedented Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) temporal revisit and sustained observation strategy for the next decades, has supported the systematic monitoring of SM at high spatial resolution ($\leq 1 \text{ km}$) and at the continental scale. In the coming years, this scenario will be further unreachd by the L-band space missions, SMAP NASA-ISRO Synthetic Aperture Radar (NISAR) and ESA Radar Observing System for Europe in L-band (ROSE-L).

In parallel, great efforts have been made to adopt and support metrological principles in environmental observations from space. It is for this reason that the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), and its space arm, the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS), endorsed in 2010, the Quality Assurance Framework for Earth Observation (QA4EO). QA4EO states the following principle regarding Earth Observation data quality: "It is critical that data and derived products are easily accessible in an open manner and have associated with them an indicator of quality traceable to reference standards (preferably SI) so users can assess suitability for their applications, i.e. the 'fitness for purpose'" (Fahy et al., 2022).

Traditionally, *in situ* SM observations have served as benchmarks for evaluating the quality of remote sensing (RS) SM products. However, systematic discrepancies often arise between these ground-based reference measurements and RS-derived SM estimates. A key challenge in comparing satellite estimated SM against *in situ* SM observations is the spatial mismatch between the point-scale (PS) *in situ* SM measurements, with a typical support of $\sim 0.1 \text{ m}$, and the satellite SM estimates. These satellite estimates are retrieved at varying resolutions (supports) –ranging from tens of kilometres (e.g., SMAP, SMOS, ASCAT) to hundreds of meters (e.g., S-1 SM). This discrepancy generates the so-called spatial representativeness uncertainty (SRU).

To limit SRU, one option is to establish core validation sites that utilize a sufficient number of PS stations to accurately represent SM at the same scale as RS-derived SM products (Colliander et al., 2021). For example, at the Apulian Tavoliere (Italy), a dense network of PS stations (e.g., Balenzano et al., 2014 & 2021) has been set up to allow upscaling the *in situ* SM observations at $\sim 1 \text{ km}$ with $\text{SRU} < 0.03 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$. Another option is to bridge the gap between PS and RS-derived SM products using *in situ* SM measurements with wider support, such as the Cosmic Ray Neutron Sensors (CRNSs).

In this document, it is first presented the comparison of SM derived from S-1 and CRNS measurements in the case of a dense network of CRNSs and the contribution of the SRU is discussed (Section 2.3).

Then, a strategy for integrating SM data at different scales, including the instrument-specific measurement uncertainties, is illustrated. In this case, the *in situ* SM are not intended as reference measurements but are combined with S-1 SM to produce a more accurate and spatially distributed estimate of SM (Section 2.4). The data fusion methods were reviewed in deliverable D7, and the Linear Weight Fusion method combined with the Inverse Distance Weighted interpolation, was selected for implementation. In deliverable D8, the data fusion method is tested over the SoMMet's high level test site in Potsdam (Germany).

2 Spaceborne and ground Soil Moisture

2.1 Materials and Methods

2.1.1 Potsdam site and CRNS soil moisture

The Potsdam site has been operated by the University of Potsdam since 2019 as part of the Cosmic Sense project, with extensive calibrations and monitoring already in place (Heistermann et al., 2023). Located in northeastern Germany, close to the village of Marquardt belonging to the city of Potsdam, it is an agricultural site with diverse vegetation cover and management across 20 field plots over 0.6 km² located at 40 m a.s.l. One weather station is located on-site. The area has a temperate climate characterized by moderate temperatures and precipitation throughout the year. The average annual precipitation is 584 mm (1981-2010), and average annual temperature is 9.3 °C (Dfb according to Beck's adjusted Köppen-Geiger's climate classification (Beck et al., 2018, 2020). Soils are mostly periglacial sand (68 to 91 %) with silt content around 8 to 27 % and clay from 0.6 to 4.4 %. The total amount of organic matter varies from 0.4 to 17.3 %.

At the Potsdam site, a dense CRNS network was operated from September 2019 to November 2022 in an area of around 10 ha. The cluster consisted of 8 permanent CRNSs and 5 temporary (< 1 yr) CRNSs. In the observation period of 2019–2022, the Potsdam site was dominated by orchards (cherry, apple) and seasonal crops (cereals, alfalfa, sugar beets, maize). The cluster was designed with significant overlap in the footprint of the CRNS, as shown in dashed line in Figure 1. Figure 2 illustrates the temporal mean of the SM values measured by each CRNS station on the S-1 acquisition dates (ascending 146 orbit) over the site.

For an extended description of all ground measurements, please refer to Heistermann et al., 2023.

Figure 1. Potsdam site, after Heistermann et al., 2023. The overlapping CRNS footprints are shown in the dashed line.

Figure 2. Mean of the soil moisture measured by the CRNS stations on the Sentinel-1 acquisition dates (Sentinel-1 ascending orbit 146) between 2019 and 2022. The error bars represent the related temporal standard deviation. The total number of soil moisture measurements per station are reported in black. Station CRNS_2 in the forest has been excluded.

2.1.2 Sentinel-1 data

S-1 Interferometric Wide (IW) Level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) High Resolution (HR) time series covering the Potsdam site and acquired from 2019 to 2022 on the 146 ascending orbit (A146) and 168 descending orbit (D168) were downloaded from the Copernicus Browser (<https://browser.dataspace.copernicus.eu/>, accessed on October 28). For pre-processing, they were calibrated, multi-looked (i.e., 4 x 4), geocoded and temporally filtered (Quegan and Yu, 2001). The final S-1 pre-processed product is characterized by an equivalent number of looks equal to or larger than ~80, a radiometric accuracy of ~1 dB, a pixel size of 40 m and a spatial resolution of ~100 m.

In Figure 3, an example of A146 and D168 S-1 images is reported. The temporal gap between consecutive S-1 images is 6 days (when both S-1A and S-1B data were available) or 12 days from end of December 2021 onwards (after the S-1B failure).

Figure 3. Examples of Sentinel-1 ascending (A146) and descending (D168) orbits covering the Potsdam site.

2.1.3 Sentinel-1 soil moisture

The SM maps were derived from S-1 co-polarized (VV) images by a short-term change detection (STCD) approach requiring SAR time series with a short revisit time, like the S-1 data (Balenzano et al., 2011). The software implementing the STCD algorithm is called “Soil MOisture retrieval from multi-temporal SAR data” (SMOSAR) (Balenzano et al., 2021). The SM retrieval is based on two main physical approximations:

- First, the retrieval is limited only to soils where the C-band SAR signal, like S-1, shows a good sensitivity to SM. This is achieved by implementing static and dynamic masking in SMOSAR. The first uses the ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) land cover at 300 m spatial resolution (<https://www.esa-landcover-cci.org/>) to obscure forests, urban areas, water bodies and permanent snow and ice. The dynamic masking conceals vegetated areas that impair the sensitivity of C-band SAR signals to SM. This is done by an adaptive thresholding method applied to S-1 cross-polarized (VH) channel (Satalino et al., 2014).
- The second approximation assumes that the change in SAR backscatter, σ , between two subsequent and closed SAR acquisitions depends only on the SM change, through the surface reflection coefficient, $\alpha_{VV}(\varepsilon, \theta)$, ratio. In this approximation, other surface parameters are regarded as constant. This assumption is based on the understanding that variables such as soil roughness, canopy structure, and vegetation biomass—which influence σ as well as

SM—typically operate on temporal scales that are significantly longer than the changes in SM caused by meteorological forcing. Therefore:

$$\frac{\sigma_{i+1}^0}{\sigma_i^0} \approx \left| \frac{\alpha_{VV}^{i+1}(\varepsilon, \theta)}{\alpha_{VV}^i(\varepsilon, \theta)} \right|^2 \approx \frac{SM_{i+1}}{SM_i} \quad (1),$$

where i identifies the temporal index in a SAR time series, ε is the relative dielectric constant of the soil, θ the radar incidence angle, VV the polarization transmitted and received and the alpha coefficient is

$$|\alpha_{VV}(\varepsilon, \vartheta)| = \left| \frac{(\varepsilon-1)(\sin^2 \vartheta - \varepsilon(1+\sin^2 \vartheta))}{(\varepsilon \cos \vartheta + \sqrt{\varepsilon - \sin^2 \vartheta})^2} \right| \quad (2).$$

From (1), it can be noted that STCD depends on relative dynamics, specifically the ratios of S-1 observations, rather than evaluating individual S-1 observations in isolation. To determine absolute SM levels, an absolute reference value is necessary. In SMOSAR, this is accomplished by calibrating S-1 data at a low resolution of 36 km. However, external sources can also be utilized for this calibration. This feature opens STCD to integration with additional local SM sources, as explained in Section 2.2.1.

Finally, SMOSAR applies a low-pass filter to obtain SM maps (mean and standard deviation) at approximately 1 km resolution (520 m pixel size).

As an example, Figure 4 zooms in on the S-1 SM map on July 4, 2021, over the Potsdam site: the mean SM on the left and the SM standard deviation (std) on the right. The CRNS locations are identified by the green points and are included in the same SMOSAR pixel (520 m), except for one that is located in a forested area. This location in the forest is masked according to the ESA CCI land cover. It is interesting to note that, in this example, the same value of the SM mean (green pixels) corresponds to different values in the SM standard deviation map (orange and blue pixels). The high SM standard deviation over Potsdam for the same SM mean value is an indication of the mixed land use of cropped fields, meadows and orchards in the area.

Figure 4. Left panel: Sentinel-1 soil moisture (SM) map on July 4, 2021, with 520 m grid spacing (corresponding to half the spatial resolution, which is ~ 1 km). Right panel: related standard deviation (std). The forested area is masked according to the ESA CCI land cover. The yellow and green points identify the CRNS in the forest and in the agricultural area, respectively.

2.2 Sentinel-1 and CRNS soil moisture comparison

The S-1 SM time series was compared against the CRNS SM. Figure 5 reports the 3-year time series of the ascending (A146) S-1 SM in red and CRNS SM in blue. The CRNS SM measurements within the S-1 SM pixel were averaged. The error bars are the standard deviation associated to the CRNS SM and S-1 SM averages. The grey line represents the daily precipitation rate, and the violet line identifies the soil temperature. For the comparison, the daily CRNS SM measurements were selected based on S-1 acquisition dates and excluding the dates with frozen soil conditions identified according to the soil temperature ($T \leq 0^\circ\text{C}$, violet line in Figure 5).

Table 1 reports the summary of the standard metrics (Entekhabi et al., 2010): root mean square error (rmse), unbiased root mean square error (ubrmse), bias and Pearson correlation (R). The S-1 SM is generally overestimated, in particular during the summer periods. Nevertheless, rmse, ubrmse and Pearson correlation are in line with results obtained comparing S-1 SM against a dense PS station network (Balenzano et al., 2021). One interesting aspect to be considered is the diversity of the S-1 and CRNS SM time sampling. There are S-1 SM peaks, e.g. on 07/09/19, 24/12/19 and 10/02/20 (highlighted in black circles in Figure 5), which were not recorded by the CRNSs. The increase detected by S-1 was due to the rain that occurred in the evening (approx. 17:00 UTC) close to or during the S-1 passages, whose effect was likely smoothed out in the daily average of the CRNS. Therefore, time diversity can affect the comparison.

Another aspect to consider is that CRNS SM measurements are integrated on a deeper penetration depth (e.g. 26.3 ± 7.7 cm on average (Köhli et al., 2015)) with respect to RS SM (< 5 cm). At the Potsdam site, only 3 locations were equipped with PS measurements at shallow depth (i.e., 5 cm) between 2019-2022. The PS sensors were calibrated by soil sample collection, reaching a calibration uncertainty of $0.03 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ (Heistermann et al., 2023). Comparing the mean PS SM and CRNS SM time series on the ascending and descending S-1 acquisition dates, it results in a Pearson correlation higher than 0.94 and rmse of $0.03 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$, excluding the days when the soil was frozen, and a bias

$<0.018 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ (CRNS measurements were wetter than PS measurements on average). This means that, for this site, CRNS measurements are quite representative of the shallow SM change, although depth diversity sensitivity still may have contributed to the rmse obtained.

Figure 5. Temporal behaviour of ascending (A146) Sentinel-1(S-1) (red line) and CRNS (blue line) soil moisture (SM). Precipitation is scaled by 100 (grey line). The soil temperature measurements are also reported on the secondary axis (purple line).

Table 1. Performance metrics comparing CRNS and ascending (A146) Sentinel-1 SM time series. R refers to the Pearson correlation, (ub)rmse is the (unbiased) root mean square error, bias is the difference between the temporal means of the CRNS and Sentinel-1 SM time series. N is the number of the S-1 acquisition dates, excluding the frozen days.

N	CRNS SM mean [m ³ /m ³]	S-1 SM mean [m ³ /m ³]	Bias (CRNS SM – S-1 SM) [m ³ /m ³]	rmse [m ³ /m ³]	ubrmse [m ³ /m ³]	R
154	0.158	0.203	-0.046	0.067	0.049	0.70

Furthermore, the dense network of CRNSs allows for investigating experimentally the impact of SRU on the uncertainty budget. Figure 6 shows the rmse (left panel) and ubrmse (right panel) between the S-1 SM and SM measured by one CRNS station or averaged from 2 up to 6 stations (excluding the CRNS with limited time series, see Figure 2). For the station groups with the same number of stations, the related (ub)rmse was evaluated and averaged, and the standard deviation was calculated. It results that the increasing number of stations (S) does not affect the rmse neither ubrmse on average. This is because the CRNS SM are extremely well correlated (Figure 7) with each other, and each station can equivalently capture the SM temporal dynamic in the Potsdam mixed agricultural area.

Conversely, the standard deviation associated to the mean rmse decreases as S increases, while the standard deviation of the mean ubrmse is limited since S=2. This is due to the fact that there is a gradient in SM temporal means measured by the CRNSs (see Figure 2), so that biases with respect to S-1 SM mean differ from station to station. Additionally, red points in Figure 6 indicate the rmse and ubrmse in case of averaging only the CRNS_4 and CRNS_22 measurements. CRNS_4 and CRNS_22 are approximately 150 m far from one another and their footprints are sufficient to cover the study area (Figure 1). This is an indication that the larger footprint of the CRNSs with respect to PS sensors may allow to minimize SRU with a limited number of instruments.

Figure 6. rmse (left panel) and ubrmse (right panel) between ascending Sentinel-1 and CRNS SM measured by 1 station or averaged from 2 up to 6 stations as a function of the number of stations (S) within the Potsdam site. The red points refer to rmse and ubrmse obtained by averaging only metrics for CRNS_4 and CRNS_22.

Figure 7. Pearson correlation between CRNS SM time series at the Potsdam site.

Figure 8 and Table 2 correspond to Figure 5 and Table 1, but for the descending (D168) S-1 SM time series. The D168 S-1 passages occur at approximately 4:00 in the morning. In winter periods, soils were mostly frozen; therefore, larger gaps in the time series can be noted. As for the ascending S-1 passages, the D168 S-1 SM is overestimated in particular during summer and, in general, metrics are worse than the A146 S-1 SM comparison. As previously noted, the presence of precipitation during the S-1 acquisitions caused an increase in SM not recorded by the CRNSs (i.e., on July 23, 2020) or limited for CRNS SM (i.e., July 7, 2022) as highlighted in the black circles.

Finally, studying SRU as a function of the number of the CRNS stations, rmse and related standard deviations behave as in Figure 6 (not shown).

Figure 8. Temporal behaviour of descending (D168) Sentinel-1(S-1) (red line) and CRNS (blue line) soil moisture (SM). Precipitation is scaled by 100 (grey line). The soil temperature measurements are also reported on the secondary axis (purple line).

Table 2. Performance metrics comparing CRNS and descending (D168) Sentinel-1 SM time series. R refers to the Pearson correlation, (ub)rmse is the (unbiased)root mean square error, bias is the difference between the temporal means of the CRNS and Sentinel-1 SM time series. N is the number of the S-1 acquisition dates, excluding the frozen days.

N	CRNS SM mean [m ³ /m ³]	S-1 SM mean [m ³ /m ³]	Bias (CRNS SM – S-1 SM) [m ³ /m ³]	rmse [m ³ /m ³]	ubrmse [m ³ /m ³]	R
135	0.156	0.215	-0.059	0.090	0.068	0.48

2.3 Sentinel-1 and CRNS soil moisture data fusion

2.3.1 Linear Weight Fusion and Inverse Distance Weighted

SMOSAR algorithm transforms time series of S-1 observations into time series of SM absolute values, under the assumption that additional information is available in terms of an estimate of the minimum value of the alpha coefficient, $|\alpha_{VV}(\epsilon, \vartheta)|$, i.e. α_{min} , during the S-1 acquisitions (Balenzano et al., 2013). There are various options to ascertain the value of α_{min} . For instance, an estimate of α_{min} at low resolution (e.g., ~40 km) can be obtained from SM operational products, e.g., SMOS, SMAP, ASCAT, etc. Another option is to use *in situ* data to drive the SM retrieval (e.g., Palmisano et al., 2020). In SMOSAR, a calibration curve expressing $|\alpha_{VV}(\epsilon, \vartheta)|^2$ values at low resolution versus S-1 backscatter at VV polarization is adopted. The rationale is that the spatial average at coarse scale (36 km × 36 km) reduces the influence of roughness and vegetation characterized by a high spatial frequency, while strengthening the relationship with SM, which adjusts steadily in space (Macelloni et al., 1999). Once α_{min} is identified, the S-1 ϵ_{SAR} can be analytically derived by equation (2) and combined with CRNS ϵ_{CRNS} . To derive ϵ_{CRNS} from CRNS SM, the Hallikainen model was used (Hallikainen et al., 1985).

Given S-1 ϵ_{SAR} and CRNS ϵ_{CRNS} and their uncertainties, $\Delta\epsilon_{SAR}$ and $\Delta\epsilon_{CRNS}$, the fused ϵ can be obtained by a linear combination of the two independent measurements (Linear Weight Fusion, LWF). The standard deviation associated with the CRNS ϵ_{CRNS} mean was adopted as $\Delta\epsilon_{CRNS}$, and $\Delta\epsilon_{SAR}$ was calculated by the Taylor uncertainty propagation as reported in Balenzano et al., 2021.

LWF was combined with the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW), as an interpolation method. Such an approach is particularly useful in integrating data sources with different extents and potential spatial gaps, as it occurs when fusing satellite and *in situ* data. In this case, to build a combined product filling the gaps, it is crucial to account for the intrinsic uncertainty of the data source and also the location of the source. The weights for each data source are based on their uncertainty and their distance (d) to the point being estimated. The combined ε at coarse scale is:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{SAR} w_{SAR} + \varepsilon_{GRD} w_{CRNS}$$

where, the weights are:

$$w_{SAR} = \frac{1}{d^a} \frac{1}{\Delta\varepsilon_{SAR}}$$

$$w_{CRNS} = \frac{1}{d^b} \frac{1}{\Delta\varepsilon_{GRD}}$$

As an example, Figure 9 shows a 36 km x 36 km interpolated pixel of ε , where the influence of ε_{CRNS} decreases with the magnitude of the uncertainties and its distance to the point being estimated. The coefficients a and b were set to 1 and 1.3, respectively.

Figure 9. Example of ε interpolated in an area of 36 km x 36 km area, derived from Sentinel-1 ε (SAR eps) with uncertainty SAR err and from CRNS measurements (in situ eps) with uncertainty in situ err.

It is also noted that even though α_{min} and the corresponding ε are derived at a coarse scale, the time series approach enables resolving at high spatial resolution SM fields undergoing a different

temporal evolution. This is because equation (1) is solved at the pixel scale in SMOSAR and, therefore, the local temporal evolution of the backscatter changes from pixel to pixel.

Figure 10 and Table 3 report the performance metrics comparing CRNS and A146 S-1 SM time series after data fusion, and correspond to Figure 5 and Table 1 but after the data fusion with the CRNS measurements. Figure 11 and Table 4 refer to the comparison of CRNS and D168 S-1 SM time series after data fusion. It can be noted that all metrics improve, in particular during the summer periods. Figure 12 shows an example of SM maps derived from S-1 alone and fused with the CRNS SM, under the hypothesis that the CRNS measurements may be representative of an area of 1000 ha. The effect of including the CRNS SM is to anchor the SM retrieval to the ground SM values to obtain more accurate (lower bias and higher Pearson correlation) results, while the satellite observations allow to efficiently spatialize the ground information in the surrounding area where no ground information is available.

Figure 10. Temporal behaviour of ascending (A146) Sentinel-1 (red line) and CRNS (blue line) soil moisture (SM) after data fusion. Precipitation (grey line) and soil temperature (purple line) measurements are also reported.

Table 3. Performance metrics comparing CRNS and ascending (A146) Sentinel-1 SM time series after data fusion. R refers to the Pearson correlation, (ub)rmse is the (unbiased) root mean square error, bias is the difference between the temporal means of the CRNS and Sentinel-1 SM time series. N is the number of the S-1 acquisition dates, excluding the frozen days.

N	CRNS SM [m ³ /m ³]	S-1 SM [m ³ /m ³]	bias (CRNS SM – S-1 SM) [m ³ /m ³]	rmse [m ³ /m ³]	ubrmse [m ³ /m ³]	R
154	0.158	0.192	-0.034	0.049	0.035	0.89

Figure 11. Temporal behaviour of descending (D168) Sentinel-1 (red line) and CRNS (blue line) soil moisture (SM) after data fusion. Precipitation (grey line) and soil temperature (purple line) measurements are also reported.

Table 4. Performance metrics comparing CRNS and descending (D168) Sentinel-1 SM time series after data fusion. R refers to the Pearson correlation, (ub)rmse is the (unbiased) root mean square error, bias is the difference between the temporal means of the CRNS and Sentinel-1 SM time series. N is the number of the S-1 acquisition dates, excluding the frozen days.

N	CRNS SM [m ³ /m ³]	S-1 SM [m ³ /m ³]	Bias (CRNS SM – S-1 SM) [m ³ /m ³]	rmse [m ³ /m ³]	ubrmse [m ³ /m ³]	R
135	0.156	0.212	-0.055	0.072	0.046	0.81

Figure 12. Example of A146 Sentinel-1 SM map on June 23, 2022 (left panel) and the fused SM map (right panel). It is supposed that CRNS measurements are representative of a larger area of approximately 1000 ha.

3 Conclusions

CRNSs have been identified as an emerging technology to support the validation of the SM derived from SAR observations (Montzka et al., 2020) as CRNSs have a larger horizontal integration of soil water content, bridging the spatial gap between satellite and point scale SM. In this study, multiscale SM measurements were compared using a 3-year SM data set. The multi scale SM measurements were derived from Copernicus S-1 images and from CRNS time series acquired over the SoMMet’s high-level test site in Potsdam. The S-1 SM maps have a 1 km spatial resolution. The specific feature of the Potsdam network with respect to other CRNS sites (e.g. Bogaen et al., ESSD, 2022) consists of the high density of CRNS stations in 1 km².

The comparison between S-1 and CRNS SM highlighted the advantage of using a network of CRNSs in order to minimize the impact of the representativeness uncertainty on metrics which generally affect the PS SM measurements when used as a reference. In this regard, the enhanced SoMMet data set at the Potsdam site (Marret et al., 2025), including both CRNSs and PS sensors, will allow

an in-depth analysis of the impact of SRU on the quality assessment of high resolution ($\leq 1\text{km}$) S-1 SM using reference measurements with different support.

Furthermore, proof of concept for CRNS SM and S-1 SM fusion was implemented, using the Linear Weight Fusion method combined with the Inverse Distance Weighted interpolation. The blending process leverages the strengths of both SM data sources to produce more accurate SM measurements at large scale. These findings highlight the potential to fuse high spatial resolution satellite observations of SM and limited number of ground SM measurements to generate SM maps applicable to thousands of hectares within irrigation/water management districts for land applications such as site-specific irrigation management (Ihuoma et al., 2021) or agricultural drought monitoring (Lv et al., 2025).

4 Appendix: Data fusion using Neural Network to retrieve new information on soil moisture

In literature, the relationship between abnormal rapid increase (bursts) of gamma background and precipitation intensity has already been observed (e.g. Mercier et al., 2009), and studies on estimating precipitation intensity by the dynamics of gamma radiation dose rate are ongoing (Yakovleva et al., 2021a, 2021b). In the same vein, in D8 a test case is provided to assess the possibility of using measured gamma radiation dose values in the natural environment to infer soil moisture (SM), fusing gamma radiation dose and SM measurements by Neural Network (NN) technique. The scientific interest relies on the fact that there is a huge network of approximately 5500 stations measuring gamma dose rate already set up in Europe (<https://remap.jrc.ec.europa.eu/Advanced.aspx>).

4.1 Method

The research was performed at the Sęków test site (Lublin Province, in eastern Poland) operated by the Institute of Agrophysics of the Polish Academy of Sciences. The test site is equipped with a set of instruments i) for monitoring SM, which is measured by several devices such as the PR2 profile probe, ii) the ELBARA (European Space Agency L-band Radiometer) device, which provides averaged SM values from an area with a radius of approximately 100 m and a temporal resolution of 4 measurements per day, iii) and the Reuter-Stokes RSS-131 ionisation chamber (HPIC), which provides gamma radiation dose rate values with a temporal resolution of 1 hour. The instruments are located on the boundary of a wetland, a meadow, and a cultivated field.

Figure A1. Left panel: ELBARA footprints for an elevation angle of 75° and azimuths 30°, 90°, 180°, and 320°. The pink dashed circles represent the upper and lower boundaries of the footprints. Right panel: the elevation angle definition of ELBARA instrument.

ELBARA is a passive radiometer working at the 1.4 GHz frequency and is designed to perform measurements of brightness temperature at two polarisations, horizontal (T_{bH}) and vertical (T_{bV}). The instrument was installed at a 6.5 m tower with the ability to move around two axes—the rotation (azimuth) from 0° to 360° (with a step of 10°), and the elevation angle (elevation) in the range from 30° to 80° (with a step of 5°). An example of ELBARA footprints for an elevation angle of 75° and azimuths 30°, 90°, 180°, and 320° is presented in Figure A1. SM was derived from ELBARA brightness temperature using the $\tau - \omega$ model (Szewczak and Łukowski, 2024).

Data collected in 2023 were used as input to create the model in the NN, while the validation model was performed on data gathered in 2024. Figure A2 shows the time series of input data obtained in 2023 and used to build the model, i.e. the SM values from the ELBARA instrument and gamma radiation dose rate values for the four azimuths. The gamma radiation dose rate values recorded in 2024 by the RSS-131 chamber, used to perform the SM retrieval, are presented in Figure A3.

Figure A2. Time series of gamma radiation dose rates in the natural environment and of the soil moisture (SM) measurements obtained using the ELBARA device for four azimuth angles: 30°, 90°, 180°, and 320°.

Figure A3. Radiation dose rate recorded in 2024 in Sęków test site.

The analysis was performed using a NN algorithm referred to as *Nonlinear autoregressive neural network with external input*, implemented in the 'narxnet' function in the Matlab environment [<https://www.mathworks.com/help/deeplearning/ref/narxnet.html>]. A schematic diagram of the process of creating a NN model using the 'narxnet' function with input data from 2023 is shown in Figure A4. Nonlinear autoregressive with external input networks can learn to predict a time series given past value of the same time series, the feedback input, and another time series called the external (or exogenous) time series. For the purposes of testing the 'narxnet' model, the input data were divided into training data (75 %), test data (15 %), and validation data (10 %). Testing was performed for 10 hidden layers of the NN.

Figure A4. Schematic diagram of the process of creating and training a neural network model using the Nonlinear autoregressive neural network with external input algorithm implemented in the 'narxnet' function in the Matlab environment.

Then, using the validated model based on data from 2023, the SM values were predicted based on radiation dose values recorded in 2024, according to the scheme presented in Figure A5.

Figure A5. Schematic diagram of the process of predicting soil moisture (SM) values in 2024, based on radiation dose data using the ‘narxnet’ model tested and validated on data from 2023.

4.2 Results

As part of creating a model using the ‘narxnet’ algorithm, statistical tests were performed to visualize the deviations between the output values obtained from the trained model (Outputs) and the conventionally true values entered the algorithm as input data (Targets), as shown in the upper part of Figure A6. The output-target differences were determined based on the assignment of data to the training, validation, or test data groups.

Figure A6. Differences between input values (Targets) and output values (Outputs) used to create the “narxnet” model for assessing the relationship between changes in radiation dose values and soil moisture.

The values of the Outputs-Targets correlation coefficients for the three data groups used in the model creation process and for the entire data set are presented in Figure A7. The correlation coefficient, R, for the training, validation, and test data groups and for the entire data set was 0.89, 0.81, 0.92, and 0.88, respectively.

Figure A7. Correlation between input data (Target) and output data (Outputs) used to develop a model of the relationship between gamma radiation dose values and changes in soil moisture. The results are presented for three data groups, i.e., training, validation, and test data, as well as for all data used (All).

The model obtained by the 'narxnet' algorithm based on input data from 2023 allowed us to generate a time series of SM changes for the Seków test site based on the time series of radiation dose changes recorded in 2024. A comparison of the SM changes from the ELBARA instrument for azimuth 30 and from the 'narxnet' model for the period in 2024 is presented in Figure A8. Analogous curves were determined for the three remaining azimuths, i.e., 90, 180, and 320.

The correlation coefficients for the time series obtained from direct measurements with the ELBARA instrument for the four azimuths considered and the corresponding soil moisture change rates obtained from the 'narxnet' model were: R=0.35, R=0.08, R=0.40, R=0.21 for directions 30, 90, 180, and 320, respectively.

Further work will be dedicated to including additional input data, such as precipitation rates, in order to improve the performance of the NN.

Figure A8. Time series of changes in average soil moisture (SM) obtained from direct measurement with the ELBARA instrument (azimuth 30, elevation 75) and obtained from the NARXNET model based on gamma radiation dose rate variability data.

5 References

- Balenzano, A., Mattia, F., Satalino, G., Lovergine, F.P., Palmisano, D., Peng, J., Marzahn, P., Wegmüller, U., Cartus, O., Dąbrowska-Zielińska, K., Musial, J.P., Davidson, M.W.J., Pauwels, V.R.N., Cosh, M.H., McNairn, H., Johnson, J.T., Walker, J.P., Yueh, S.H., Entekhabi, D., Kerr, Y.H., Jackson, T.J., 2021. Sentinel-1 soil moisture at 1 km resolution: a validation study. *Remote Sens Environ* 263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112554>
- Balenzano, A., Satalino, G., Iacobellis, V., Gioia, A., Manfreda, S., Rinaldi, M., De Vita, P., Miglietta, F., Toscano, P., Annicchiarico, G., Mattia, F., 2014. A ground network for SAR-derived soil moisture product calibration, validation and exploitation in Southern Italy, in: *International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2014.6947206>
- Balenzano, A., Satalino, G., Lovergine, F., Rinaldi, M., Iacobellis, V., Mastronardi, N., Mattia, F., 2013. On the use of temporal series of L- and X-band SAR data for soil moisture retrieval. Capitanata plain case study. *Eur J Remote Sens* 46. <https://doi.org/10.5721/EuJRS20134643>
- Balenzano, A., Satalino, G., Pauwels, V., Mattia, F., 2011. Soil moisture retrieval from dense temporal series of C-band SAR data over agricultural sites, in: *International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)*. pp. 3136–3139.
- Beck, H.E., Zimmermann, N.E., McVicar, T.R., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A., Wood, E.F., 2020. Publisher Correction: Present and future Köppen-Geiger climate classification maps at 1-km resolution (*Scientific Data*, (2018), 5, 1, (180214), 10.1038/sdata.2018.214). *Sci Data* 7, 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-00616-w>
- Beck, H.E., Zimmermann, N.E., McVicar, T.R., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A., Wood, E.F., 2018. Present and future köppen-geiger climate classification maps at 1-km resolution. *Sci Data* 5, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.214>
- Colliander, A., Reichle, R.H., Crow, W.T., Cosh, M.H., Chen, F., Chan, S., Das, N., Bindlish, R., Chaubell, J., Liu, Q., Neill, P.O., Dunbar, R.S., Dang, L., Kimball, J., Jackson, T.J., Jassar, H.K., Asanuma, J., Berg, A., Bosch, D.D., Caldwell, T., Calvet, J., Collins, C.H., Livingston, S., McNairn, H., Moghaddam, M., Montzka, C., Pellarin, T., Pfeil, I., Pulliainen, J., Ramos, J., Seyfried, M., Starks, P., Su, Z., Velde, R. Van Der, Zeng, Y., Thibeault, M., Vreugdenhil, M., Walker, J.P., Zribi, M., Entekhabi, D., Yueh, S., 2021. Validation of Soil Moisture Data Products from the NASA SMAP Validation of Soil Moisture Data Products from the NASA SMAP Mission Mission. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.14714571.v1>
- Entekhabi, B.D., Njoku, E.G., Neill, P.E.O., Kellogg, K.H., Crow, W.T., Edelstein, W.N., Entin, J.K., Goodman, S.D., Jackson, T.J., Johnson, J., Kimball, J., Piepmeier, J.R., Koster, R.D., Martin, N., McDonald, K.C., Moghaddam, M., Moran, S., Reichle, R., Shi, J.C., Spencer, M.W., Thurman, S.W., Tsang, L., Zyl, J. Van, 2010. The Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) Mission. *Proceedings of the IEEE* 98.
- Entekhabi, D., Reichle, R.H., Koster, R.D., Crow, W.T., 2010. Performance Metrics for Soil Moisture Retrievals and Application Requirements. *J Hydrometeorol* 11, 832–840. <https://doi.org/10.1175/2010JHM1223.1>
- Fahy, J., Fox, N., Gardiner, T., Green, P., Hunt, S., Mittaz, J., Mota, B., De Vis, P., Woolliams, E., 2022. General guidance on a metrological approach to fundamental data records (FDR), thematic data products (TDP) and fiducial reference measurements (FRM).
- Hallikainen, M.T., Ulaby, F.T., Dobson, M.C., El-rayes, M.A., Wu, L., 1985. Microwave dielectric behavior of wet soil-Part I: Empirical models and experimental observations. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sensing*, vol. GE-23 ge-23, 25–34.
- Heistermann, M., Francke, T., Scheffele, L., Dimitrova Petrova, K., Budach, C., Schrön, M., Trost, B., Rasche, D., Güntner, A., Döpper, V., Förster, M., Köhli, M., Angermann, L., Antonoglou, N., Zude-Sasse, M., Oswald, S.E., 2023. Three years of soil moisture observations by a

- dense cosmic-ray neutron sensing cluster at an agricultural research site in north-east Germany. *Earth Syst Sci Data* 15, 3243–3262. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-3243-2023>
- Ihuoma, S.O., Madramootoo, C.A., Kalacska, M., 2021. Integration of satellite imagery and in situ soil moisture data for estimating irrigation water requirements. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2021.102396>
- Kerr, Y.H., Waldteufel, P., Wigneron, J.-P., Delwart, S., Cabot, F., Boutin, J., Escorihuela, M.-J., Font, J., Reul, N., Gruhier, C., Juglea, S.E., Drinkwater, M.R., Hahne, A., Martín-Neira, M., Mecklenburg, S., 2010. The SMOS Mission: New Tool for Monitoring Key Elements of the Global Water Cycle. *Proceedings of the IEEE* 98, 666–687. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2010.2043032>
- Köhli, M., Schrön, M., Zreda, M., Schmidt, U., Dietrich, P., Zacharias, S., 2015. Footprint characteristics revised for field-scale soil moisture monitoring with cosmic-ray neutrons. *Water Resour Res* 51, 5772–5790. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/2015WR017169>
- Lv, A., Yang, X., Zhang, W., Han, Y., 2025. Integrated soil moisture fusion for enhanced agricultural drought monitoring in China. *Agric Water Manag* 311, 109401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2025.109401>
- Macelloni, G., Paloscia, S., Pampaloni, P., Sigismondi, S., De Matthaeis, P., Ferrazzoli, P., Schiavon, G., Solimini, D., 1999. The SIR-C/X-SAR experiment on Montespertoli: Sensitivity to hydrological parameters. *Int J Remote Sens* 20, 2597–2612.
- Mercier, J.F., Tracy, B.L., d'Amours, R., Chagnon, F., Hoffman, I., Korpach, E.P., Johnson, S., Ungar, R.K., 2009. Increased environmental gamma-ray dose rate during precipitation: a strong correlation with contributing air mass. *J Environ Radioact* 100, 527–533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2009.03.002>
- Marret, E., Grosse, P. M., Scheffele, L., Dimitrova Petrova, K., Francke, T., Altdorff, D., Heistermann, M., Schiel, M., Neumann, C., Scheffler, D., Saberioon, M., Kunz, M., Zboril, M., Marach, J., Reginatto, M., Balenzano, A., Rasche, D., Stumpp, C., Trost, B., and Oswald, S. E.: The Potsdam Soil Moisture Observatory: High-coverage reference observations at kilometer scale, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2025-546>, in review, 2025.
- Montzka, C., Cosh, M., Bayat, B., Bitar, A. Al, Berg, A., Bogena, H.R., Bolten, J.D., Cabot, F., Caldwell, T., Chan, S., Colliander, A., Crow, W., Das, N., Lannoy, G. De, Dorigo, W., Steven, R., Gruber, A., Hahn, S., Jagdhuber, T., Jones, S., Kerr, Y., Kim, S., Koyama, C., Kurum, M., Lopez-baeza, E., Mattia, F., Mccoll, K.A., Mecklenburg, S., Mohanty, B., Neill, P.O., Or, D., Petropoulos, G.P., Piles, M., Reichle, R.H., Rodriguez-fernandez, N., Rüdiger, C., Scanlon, T., Schwartz, R.C., Spengler, D., Srivastava, P., Suman, S., Schalie, R. Van Der, Wagner, W., Wegmüller, U., Wigneron, J., 2020. Soil Moisture Product Validation Good Practices Protocol Version 1.0. Good Practices for Satellite Derived Land Product Validation, 123, https://lpvs.gsfc.nasa.gov/PDF/CEOS_SM_LPV_Protocol_V1_20201027_final.pdf.
- Palmisano, D., Mattia, F., Satalino, G., Pierdicca, N., Monti-Guarnieri, A.V., 2020. Sentinel-1 Sensitivity to Soil Moisture at High Incidence Angle and the Impact on Retrieval over Seasonal Crops. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.* in press.
- Quegan, S., Yu, J.J., 2001. Filtering of Multichannel SAR Images. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 39, 2373–2379.
- Satalino, G., Balenzano, A., Mattia, F., Davidson, M.W.J., 2014. C-band SAR data for mapping crops dominated by surface or volume scattering. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters* 11, 384–388.
- Szewczak, K., Łukowski, M., 2024. Medium-Scale Soil Moisture Retrievals Using an ELBARA L-Band Radiometer Using Time-Dependent Parameters for Wetland-Meadow-Cropland Site. *Remote Sens (Basel)* 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16122200>
- Wagner, W., Hahn, S., Kidd, R., Melzer, T., Bartalis, Z., Hasenauer, S., Figa-Saldaña, J., De Rosnay, P., Jann, A., Schneider, S., Komma, J., Kubu, G., Brugger, K., Aubrecht, C., Züger, J., Gangkofner, U., Kienberger, S., Brocca, L., Wang, Y., Blöschl, G., Eitzinger, J.,

Steinnocher, K., Zeil, P., Rubel, F., 2013. The ASCAT soil moisture product: A review of its specifications, validation results, and emerging applications. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift* 22, 5–33. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2013/0399>

Yakovleva, V., Yakovlev, G., Parovik, R., Zelinskiy, A., Kobzev, A., 2021a. Rainfall intensity and quantity estimation method based on gamma-dose rate monitoring. *Sensors* 21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21196411>

Yakovleva, V., Zelinskiy, A., Parovik, R., Yakovlev, G., Kobzev, A., 2021b. Model for reconstruction of γ -background during liquid atmospheric precipitation. *Mathematics* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math9141636>